

Exploring the Impact of Community Education Programmes on Socio-Economic Empowerment in Rivers State

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ABSTRACT

The prevalence rate of low-income earners in Rivers state requires urgent education measures. Community education programmes therefore possessed the capacity to positively impact on the socio-economic well-being of the people. Thus, the study explored the impact of community education programmes on the socio-economic empowerment of residence in Rivers State. The study adopted the descriptive research design, to generate data from a sample of one hundred and twelve (112) respondents which includes programmes participants, facilitators, and community leaders, through questionnaire and document reviews. Four communities were randomly selected in Abua-Odual, Ahoada East, Ahoada West and Ogba-Egbema-Ndoni local government areas of the state. The findings of the study revealed the positive impact of community education programmes on socio-economic empowerment of individuals in Rivers State. Also, it was indicated that community education programmes have the potentials of increasing access to education, skills development, and prospects for entrepreneurship, which is capable of reducing the surging rate of poverty ravaging the state and thus improve the economic status of the people. Besides, the study stimulated participation as a means of social inclusion, which is capable of enhancing social cohesion and community development process. Nevertheless, the study also identified some of the challenges confronting community education programmes in Rivers State. Finally, the findings of the study have some far-reaching implications for community development process in Rivers State, Nigeria.

Keywords: Education, Impact, Economic Well-being, Development Process.

INTRODUCTION

Economic empowerment is one of the thoughtful areas in the global concern to improve the social system. The reason for the concern is not unconnected with the need to end poverty in all of its forms in the society as contained in goal one of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). To achieve the process therefore, entails acquiring economic relevance or power that will enable the people to deepen their consciousness as a necessary means to assert full economic control (Oluwole, 2013). The implicit assumption behind the assertion is to enhanced per capital income and to promote socio-economic status of the people in relation to others, based on income, education and occupation (Burchi, 2006 & Olofinniyi et al,2021). Accordingly, socio-economic empowerment mostly involves the interactions between social and economic factors such as education, employment, status and access to social services among others to shape the social system. It is regarded as a process of positive change through a participatory decision-making process for effective production and distribution of services (Onyeozu, Aruma & Wordu ,2016). Based on this note, the process is perceived as a fundamental human right that enables a dignified and fulfilled life. Moreso, socio-economic empowerment serves as a major key that drives growth and

development of the society. However, the process has remained a challenge to many individuals and communities in the State. Notwithstanding, one of the critical factors that has been identified as a potential tool for addressing the challenges is community education programmes. Accordingly, community education is an aspect of adult education and a tool which promotes lifelong learning, social change and community development process. While these concepts are relative to community education, there are varying views about them (Onyeozu, Aruma & Wordu, 2016). It is a type of education needed to ensure the self-confidence, self-respect and personal independence as well as a process to safeguard human rights and achieve social equality; and is equally an indispensable tool in motivating active participation in socio-cultural, political and economic activities that enables improvement of quality of life. In this regard, educational profiles reveal that most nations of the world accord great importance to adult and community education as a springboard for national development (Maranzu & Maranzu, 2019). In this vein, Ezimah (2004) explained that the process is one that is aimed at raising consciousness, providing understanding on issues and offering the necessary skills in areas such as human and material resources for the overall development of the community. Community Education is also seen as an organised learning activities that focuses on all other areas of learning such as literacy education, extra-mural classes, continuing education of all categories, vocational training, health, re-creation, citizenship, cultural activities, refresher courses among other activities, with the adult serving as its primary learner and the community as the context. The implication of the programmes is aimed at empowering and enunciating needs and solving community problems. By this assumption community education is regarded as a type of lifelong education rather than simple education for source of revenue. (Maranzu & Maranzu, 2019). Harris (2009) perceived community education as a learning and training process that provide opportunities for personal as well as general development of the community. It is one of the vital strategies that is often used to alleviate people out of the borderline of poverty. Community education is also seen as a cornerstone for rapid development, because it serves the purpose of providing the requisite knowledge, capacity and skills for economic empowerment. Besides, Mbalisi (2016) identified the process as a problem-solving enterprise which is capable of rejuvenating people's abilities for the purpose of growth and development. As a very supportive process, it provides the necessary information and services, that is not only meant for self-sufficient and independent processes, but also for collaborative learning and problem-solving abilities. Besides, the process is regarded as one with the capacity of enhancing the effectiveness of open learning system that redresses the imbalance in society (Adedokun, 2008 & Abiona 2012). This implies, that education/learning brings to bear the rich experiences and innovations that support individuals' capacities to attain national development. Besides, it is not only a social service but a transformative process that is fundamental to self-help, responsible practices and enlightenment of the people towards the eradication of poverty and other associated economic misfortunes (Ayodele & Adedokun, 2012 and Etigbamo, 2019). According to Adebowale et al. (2019), the programmes play a crucial role in providing learning opportunities for marginalized group to gain skills and knowledge for their economic self-sufficiencies. The process is equally observed to have assisted in improving the access to education and the reduction in the rate of illiteracy. Thus, Okoronkwo and Mbajiorgu (2018), explained community education programmes as a type of education that has contributed positively to the economic development of the people. Because it has assisted in equipping most participants with appropriate skills and knowledge required to function as entrepreneurs. The increasing rate of small and medium-sized enterprises, has led to job creation and poverty reduction. It is a pragmatic programme that boost the requisite social capital and bonding among individuals for enhanced growth and development process (Adegbija & Adetona, 2018).

Regrettably, in spite of these enormous potential benefits of the programmes, it has been observed that there are several challenges impeding the success of community education in the state. According to Maranzu & Maranzu (2019) the abysmal ignorance of the meaning of community education exposes it to broader definition so that it loses clarity and effectiveness. Thus, there has been a misleading judgement of what the entire purview of community education can achieve for national development. Adebowale et al. (2019), identified other challenges as lack of government support, inadequate funding, limited services

and infrastructure provision among others. Maranzu and Maranzu (2019) enumerated the underlying problems facing the promotion of community education in Nigeria as follows:

1. lack of political will on the part of the government to support the education system. Unlike the formal education system, non-formal community education has not been enjoying enough fund from the government.
2. another problem is that no considerable effort has been made to professionalized community education where experts, such as adult educators, community educators and social welfare officials are meant to provide government with professional advice on community education issues. Rather, people without the requisite knowledge of community education were often recruited or engaged.
3. With the dearth in the provisions of relevant books and other materials, community educators with little or no training in the profession often find themselves in great dilemma. Therefore, making essential community education programmes ineffective to the beneficiaries, because those appointed to handle the programmes lack the expertise on the *modus operandi* of community education.

Also, the issue of gender gap in most community programmes as may be encouraged by social factors such as culture, values or economic status encumbers the anticipated outcomes. Accordingly, these negative worldviews on some folks during community programmes poses grave challenge to the process of empowerment. Therefore, economic empowerment should encompass all and sundry for better outcomes. For this reason, stepping up emphasis on community education as a strong instrument for the enablement of local communities to take charge of their own development process is very necessary. It is against this backdrop, that the study seeks to explore the impact of community education programmes on socio-economic empowerment in Rivers State.

Statement of the Problem

The areas forming the focus of this study, is one of the oil and gas business hubs of the state. With the introduction of various community education programmes by successive administrations to improve socio-economic empowerment in the area, it has been observed that not much has been achieved. It is on this basis that this study is set out to examine existing research gap on the overall impact of community education programmes on the economic status of the beneficiaries. Specifically, the lack of comprehensive studies evaluating the effectiveness of these programmes to achieve stated objectives has remain a major problem. Thus, the need to examine the extent to which the programmes are sustainably administered to achieve local needs or context, will address the gaps in knowledge and provide stakeholders with valuable insights. Therefore, to explore the impact of community education programmes on socio-economic empowerment in Rivers State is the problem of this study.

Aims and Objectives of the Study

The aim of this study is to explore the impact of community education programmes on socio-economic empowerment in Rivers State. The specific objectives are to:

1. identify the essential community education programmes for socio-economic empowerment in Rivers State
2. examine the impact of community education programmes on socio-economic status of participants in Rivers State
3. assess the challenges of community education programmes for socio-economic empowerment in Rivers State

Aims and Objectives of the Study

The following research questions guided this study:

1. what are the essential community education programmes for socio-economic empowerment in Rivers State?
2. What are the impacts of community education programmes on socio-economic status of participants in Rivers State?

3. What are the challenges of community education programmes for socio-economic empowerment in Rivers State?

Hypothesis

1. There is no significant difference between community education programmes and the impacts on socio-economic status of participants in Rivers State

Theoretical Framework

The study is anchored on the Human Capital and the Social Capital Theories propounded by Theodore W. Schultz in 1961 and Gary S. Becker in 1962 and Pierre Bourdieu in 1977 respectively. The Human Capital Theory suggests individuals' stocking of knowledge, skills, and abilities as a determining factor for earning higher income. This theory proposes that investments in education and training can effectively improve the human capital for economic opportunities. Thus, community education is aimed at enhancing knowledge and skills for socio-economic empowerment. On the other hand, Social Capital Theory argues that social networks, relationships, and norms are influenced by individuals' access to resources and the ability to pursue economic opportunities. This theory contends that strong social networks enable better chance of accessing local resources and support, that facilitate socio-economic empowerment. Community education programmes serve as a strong platform for social networks and relationships. Thus, providing the needed interactions and collaborative relationships necessary for accessing economic opportunities. The implications of the theories presuppose the impact of educational interventions on the overall economic empowerment of the people.

METHODOLOGY

The research approach adopted in the study was a descriptive survey to assess the mean responses of residents in selected local government areas of Rivers State. The local government areas are Abua-Odua, Ahoada East, Ahoada West and Ogba-Egbema-Ndoni. The target population comprised the entire 1,120 residents in the area who have participated in community education programmes for socio-economic empowerment. Four communities each in the selected local government areas was used in the study. A sample size of 112 (10% of the population) was purposively selected using stratified random sampling techniques. A Questionnaire titled: Exploring the Impact of Community Education Programmes on the Socio-Economic Empowerment (ETICEPSEEQ) was adopted to elicit responses for the study. The instrument was a 21-item questionnaire consisting of three sections with information to meet the demands of the research questions. The instrument measured the essential components, impact and as well as the challenges of community education programmes for socio-economic empowerment in the area. The instrument was validated by experts in the field of adult and non-formal education. T-test reliability technique was used to obtain a reliability index of 0.83 using Pearson Product Moment correlation coefficient (PPMC). The mean statistics was used to analyzed data collected. Mean equal to or greater than 2.5 was used in making decision on item, while the null hypothesis was tested using t-test at 0.05 level of significance.

DATA ANALYSIS

Research Question One: *What are the essential community education programmes for socio-economic empowerment in Rivers State?*

Table 1: Mean scores on the essential community education programmes for socio-economic empowerment in Rivers State

S/N	Item Statement	Total	Mean	SD	Remark
1	Adult literacy programme	384	3.69	0.83	Agree
2	Vocational training programmes	360	3.46	0.91	Agree
3	Financial literacy programme	346	3.33	1.13	Agree
4	Leadership development program	355	3.41	1.12	Agree
5	Entrepreneurship development programme	358	3.44	1.06	Agree
6	Health and wellness education	353	3.39	0.84	Agree
7	Environmental education	352	3.38	0.98	Agree

Table 1 showed that all 7 items relating to essential community education programmes for socio-economic empowerment received mean rating of 2.5 and above. Using the benchmark of 2.5 for decision, the data in the table above suggest that the whole items were perceived as a very essential components of community education programmes in Rivers State.

Research Question Two: *What are the impacts of community education programmes on socio-economic empowerment in Rivers State?*

Table 2: Means scores on the impacts of community education programmes on socio-economic empowerment in Rivers State

S/N	Item Statement	Total	Mean	SD	Remark
1	Adult literacy programme helps to improve literacy level	382	3.67	0.86	Agree
2	Vocational education programme enables people acquire varying employable life vocational skill	373	3.57	0.96	Agree
3	Financial literacy programme fosters entrepreneurship skills	331	3.18	1.26	Agree
4	Leadership development programme raises awareness on prevailing social issues	340	3.27	1.07	Agree
5	Entrepreneurship development programme enhances poverty reduction	388	3.25	1.08	Agree
6	Health and wellness education enables informed decision-making process for overall well being	395	3.80	1.56	Agree
7	Environmental education encourages the development of skills/knowledge for sustainable livelihood	346	3.33	1.0	Agree

The data in Table 2 showed that respondents rated the impacts of community education programmes on socio-economic empowerment high in Rivers State. This implies that responses on all the items reechoed the impact of community education programmes on socio-economic empowerment. This was supported by the standard deviation which ranged between 0.86 and 1.96.

Research Question Three: *What are the challenges of community education programmes for socio-economic empowerment in Rivers State?*

Table 3: Means scores on the challenges of community education programmes for socio-economic empowerment in Rivers State.

S/N	Item Statement	Total	Mean	SD	Remark
1	Lack of clarity on the meaning of community education	306	2.94	1.27	Agree
2	Misleading judgement on the view of community education	300	2.88	1.25	Agree
3	Lack of political will to provide financial assistance	312	3.12	0.92	Agree
4	Low engagement in decision making process	301	2.89	1.19	Agree
5	Inadequate provisions of relevant learning materials	311	2.99	1.28	Agree
6	Poor collaboration among key stakeholders the programme	328	3.15	1.20	Agree
7	Community education Programmes are manifested in various forms/context	264	2.54	1.51	Agree

The analysis of data on research question 3 as contained in the table above shows the computed mean scores on the challenges of community education programmes for socio-economic empowerment in Rivers State. The analysis of data for item 1,2,3,4,5,6 and 7 shows positive responses with mean scores and standard deviation of 2.94 and 1.27, 2.88 and 1.25, 3.0 and 0.92, 2.89 and 1.19, 2.99 and 1.28, 3.15 and 1.20, and 2.54 and 1.51 respectively above the set criterion mean of 2.50, which is an indication of the existence of enormous challenges on community education programmes for socio-economic empowerment.

Hypothesis: *There is no significant difference between community education programmes and their impacts on socio-economic empowerment in Rivers State*

Table 4: T-test calculation on community education programmes and their impacts on socio-economic empowerment in Rivers State

Variables	N	X	SD	df	t-cal	t-crit	Level of sign.	Decision
Community education programmes	7	3.44	0.35					
Impacts on socio-economic empowerment	7	2.91	0.19	104	0.16	2.36	0.05	Accepted

The data on table 4 showed the mean scores of respondents on the variables was 3.44 and 2.91. The data further revealed through t-test analysis that there is no significant difference between community education programmes and their impacts on socio-economic empowerment in Rivers State. The result of the analysis is an indication that the t-calculated is less than the t-critical value of ± 2.36 . Therefore, the null hypothesis is hereby accepted. This implies that there is no significant difference between essential community education programmes and their impacts on socio-economic empowerment in Rivers State.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Evidence from the results of this findings as indicated in table 1 showed clearly that all the respondents, agreed that all the items listed in the table are the various essential community education programmes for socio-economic empowerment in Rivers State. This finding is in line with the observation of Harris (2009) that community education programmes are essential training opportunities for personal and general development of the community. It is a vital strategy that is aimed at alleviating people out of the borderline of poverty. It is also seen as an organised learning activities that focuses on all other areas of learning such as literacy education, extra-mural classes, continuing education of all categories, vocational training, health, re-creation, citizenship, cultural activities, refresher courses among others activities, with the adult serving as its primary learner and the community as context (Maranzu & Maranzu, 2019). Besides, Mbalisi (2016) identified the process as a problem-solving enterprise which is capable of rejuvenating people's abilities for the purpose of growth and development.

The result in Table 2 revealed the impacts of community education programmes for socio-economic empowerment as a process of improving literacy levels of the people, enabling the acquisitions of varying employable life vocational skills, fostering financial literacy for entrepreneurship skills, raising awareness on prevailing social issues, enhances poverty reduction, enables informed decision-making process for overall well-being and encourages the development of skills/knowledge for sustainable livelihood. This finding corroborated with the statement of Okoronkwo and Mbajiorgu (2018), that community education programmes are very impactful to the economic development of people, because it equips people with the appropriate skills and knowledge to function for national growth and development. Ezimah (2004) explained that the process is one that is aimed at raising consciousness, providing understanding on issues and offering the necessary skills in areas such as human and material resources for the overall development of the community. Adegbija and Adetona (2018) therefore supported the fact that community education programmes possess the tendencies to empower individuals, particularly women and youths for decision-making and community development process. Thus, boosting the requisite social capital and bonding among community members to enhanced development process.

On the challenges of community education programmes for socio-economic empowerment in Rivers State, findings revealed the existence of several challenges. These existing challenges as indicated by the respondents are lack of clarity on the meaning of community education, misleading judgement on the view of community education, lack of political will to provide financial assistance, low engagement in decision making process, inadequate provisions of relevant learning materials, poor collaboration among key stakeholders of the programme and the manifestation of community education Programmes in various forms/context. The finding in agreement with Adebowale et al. (2019), asserted some of the challenges affecting community education programmes as lack of government support, inadequate funding, limited services and infrastructure among others. It is equally justified by Maranzu and Maranzu (2019) that these underlying problems hinders the *modus operandi* of community education in Nigeria. The implication of the findings re-echoed the need to urgently address the various issues negatively affecting learning that improves socio-economic status of people in the state.

Nevertheless, the analysis of difference between the mean responses on the essential community education programmes and the impacts on socio-economic empowerment in Rivers State indicated no significance difference. This implies that there was no disagreement in the views of respondents on essential community education programmes and the impacts on socio-economic empowerment in Rivers state.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of this study, the essential areas of community education programmes for socio-economic empowerment in the state has been identifies as adult literacy, vocational training, financial literacy and leadership development programmes among others. In respect to the impacts of the programmes, the study concluded in a high note of agreement by respondents on the impacts on socio-economic empowerment. The study also indicated the impacts of community education programmes on

socio-economic empowerment as one that is very vital for the overall well-being of the people. Furthermore, the study established the various challenges confronting community education programmes for socio-economic empowerment in the state. Based on this valuable information, there is need to pay a serious attention on community education programmes to achieve improved and sustainable livelihood for the people.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made:

1. Government should ensure conducive atmosphere for the investment of non-state actors in the design and implementation of context specific community education programmes to assist in the improvement of socio-economic status of the people.
2. The government should create a robust framework for monitory and impact evaluation system to ensure transparency, accountability and sustainable learning process.
3. Government and other stakeholders should proactively collaborate to address existing systematic and cultural barriers to participation in education programmes.

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